

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ENTREPRENEURIAL STATUS, ECONOMIC MOTIVATION AND
BUSINESS START-UP OF UNDERGRADUATE BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN FEDERAL
UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH EAST, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study aimed at determining the Relationship Between Entrepreneurial status, Economic motivation and Business Start-Up of Undergraduate Business Education students in North east, Nigeria. Two null hypotheses guided the study. Survey research design was used for the study; area of the study is North east geopolitical zone of Nigeria, the population of the study comprised of 998 final year undergraduates' business education students. Stratified proportionate sampling technique was used for the study. Instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Relationship between Entrepreneurial status, Economic motivation and Business Startup (RBESEMBS). The instrument used in this study was validated by experts, reliability of the instrument was determined through Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient of .823 was obtained. The data were collected by the researcher assisted by 3 research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using simple linear regression to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the test of null hypotheses revealed that there is significant relationship between entrepreneurial status and business start up of undergraduate business education students. Also, the result revealed that there is significant relationship between economic motivation and business start up of undergraduate business education students. Based on this the study recommended among others that, the federal government of Nigeria, National University Commission (NUC) should put in place every mechanism that will increase and motivate the development of Entrepreneurial status and support funding for business start-up of undergraduate business education students of federal universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Keywords: Business startup, Entrepreneurship, Education, Status, Motivation, Relationship

Introduction

The goal of Entrepreneurship education is in line with that of the National Policy on Education FRN (2013) which emphasized on developing intellectual capacity and values for the individual survival that will provide enabling environment to acquire both physical and intellectual skills for self-reliance and becoming useful members of the society. A profitable and sustainable business creation is possible only through entrepreneurship education which offers essential skill, motivation and awareness to the students (Salihu, 2016). Also, Aliu (2014) stated that Entrepreneurship Education is a learning directed towards developing in young people those skills, competencies, understandings, and attributes which equip them to be innovative, and training them to identify, create, initiate, and successfully manage personal and or community business, and work opportunities, including working for themselves. While Cole, Rebel, Tatyana and Sokolyk (2014) describe business

start-up as organizations established to search for repeatable and scalable business models. Start-up according to Ries (2011) is any organization aiming at creation of new product or services in condition of extreme uncertainty.

Therefore, in Business start-up who is potential entrepreneurs among the undergraduate business education students may be motivated to start a business but lack the entrepreneurial status and economic motivation to venture into a new business. Today's realities indicate that there is no government of any country that can absolutely provide job to absorb all graduates from her tertiary institutions. Entrepreneurship education inculcates entrepreneurial skills in individuals that enable them confront situations in creative and innovative ways (Chiaha & Agu, 2013).

Therefore, it can be deduced that the aimed of entrepreneurship education in the Nigerian universities is defeated since after undergoing entrepreneurship education training in the universities in order to instilled in them to become self-reliant after graduation, yet the students continue to roam about looking for white collar jobs after graduation, which is not readily available. Because of these, this study would attempt to established the relationship between entrepreneurial status, economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students in universities in North east, Nigeria.

Entrepreneurial activities, when pursued strategically, have the capacity to generate high revenue leading to significant profit for the entrepreneur to enjoy, thus economic motivation comes into the picture. The need to make money has also been singled out as the main driver leading to individuals pursuing entrepreneurial activities (Kuratko, 2016). Moreover, based on start-up indicators by country, the motivations for start-ups are classified as economic and non-economic motivations. Economic motivation means pursuing external compensation, such as monetary compensation, social recognition, high status, and a good reputation through entrepreneurial activities. By contrast, non-economic motivation means pursuing individual interests and satisfaction through the entrepreneurial process (Frederiksen & Brem, 2017).

The entrepreneurs who have entrepreneurial status background have a better understanding of business opportunities, and they have a strong influence on the decision to support the activities. Family support and peer influence also enhances individual intention to launch start-ups (Edelman, *et al.*, 2016). People with financial and moral support from their families are more psychologically stable and are better decision makers. An entrepreneur who has family member support is ready to face all of the challenges that are involved in the project execution process (Mustapha & Selvaraju, 2015). Business start up acknowledges the role of entrepreneurial status in attracting students to start a business. Family support always gives strength to individuals and helps them to develop an entrepreneurial attitude (Xu, *et al.*, 2020). Family support rescues the young entrepreneur from job-related issues by supporting their business start-ups (Hahn, *et al.*, 2020).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between entrepreneurial status, economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between entrepreneurial status and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?
2. Determine the relationship between economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Entrepreneurial status and business start-up of undergraduate business education student of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Literature review

Theory of social changes

The theory of social changes was developed by Everret Hagens (1963) as an endeavour to explain how individual change their social status in order to gain societal respect. The core notion that drives this sociological theory is that when an individual feel that they are no longer respected by the society, they tend to implement innovative ways by means which the social status can get positively transformed. The aim is to regain their lost status. This desire to change the prevailing social status can be indicated as the acquired tendency of an individual to become an entrepreneur. Thus, this theory emphatically shows that withdrawal from existing social status acts as a driven which influences entrepreneurial qualities in an individual from an ordinary person to an entrepreneur (Everret, 1963).

Therefore, theory of social changes is related to this study because it deals with how individual change their social status in order to gain societal respect, that can lead to entrepreneurial motivation such as innovation that also lead to new venture creation. The theory of social changes also indicated that the core notion that drives this sociological theory is that when an individual feel that they are no longer respected by the society, they tend to implement innovative ways by means which their social status can get positively transformed the aim is to regain their lost status. Also, business startup success is better understood by recognizing the entrepreneurial status of an individual success as entrepreneurs.

In another study conducted by Akhter and Sumi (2014), it was revealed that the socio-cultural factor has a significant effect on entrepreneurship activities. There seems to be a consensus on the proposition that the family is the primary agent of socialization. Parents are seen as role models exercising both overt and covert technical influence on their wards as they set norms, values and orient behaviours in the course of daily life. Thus, the children on daily basis observe and imbibe certain latent values passed on to them by their parents, all of which shape their future personality and career. This signals the likely significant influence of family entrepreneurial history on student's business interest.

Entrepreneurs require financial support to diversify their start-up risks, obtain the start-up capital and finance growth and expansion. In many developing and emerging economies there are only few sources for financing and entrepreneurs might be prevented from starting a business as they do not receive the required finances (Juliane & Julia, 2014). When a potential entrepreneur thinks about starting a new venture, he or she has to consider their potential market and if there are any entry regulations. This refers to market dynamics (level of change in the market) and the market openness (extent to which new firms are able to enter the market) GEM framework in (Amoros & Bosman, 2014). In addition, it is relevant for the entrepreneur that there is required physical infrastructure which refers to the ease or difficulty of accessing physical resources such as land, space, electricity, communication or transportation GEM framework in (Amoros & Bosman, 2014).

Methodology

The Research Design for this study was survey design. Survey design is concerned with finding, describing and interpreting the outcomes of the research. The design is relevant in quantitative research method because it allows for objective observation, reporting and analyzing of issues the way they are without any form of subjectivity (Sambo, 2005). The study

was carried out in North-east Geo-political zone of Nigeria, which comprises six (6) states namely; Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe states respectively. The population of the study comprised 998 final year undergraduate business education students that acquired mandatory training on entrepreneurship education from three selected Federal Universities in the North-east, Nigeria. Three Federal Universities that are offering business education were selected as the sample for this study and the study used Stratified proportionate sampling technique for the purpose of this study. The sample size of the study is 278 drawn from the population of 998 students based on Krejcie & Morgan, (1970).

The instrument used in this study for the data collection was adapted and modified from previous literature (Cristian *et al.*, 2016; Jayawarma *et al.*, 2013; Krasniqi & Tullami, 2013) and was administered to the final year undergraduate business education students from the three selected Federal Universities that are offering business education in the North-east, Nigeria. The questionnaire is titled Relationship between Entrepreneurial status, economic motivation and business start up (RBEMBSQ).

The instrument used in this study was subjected to face validation. The validation was conducted by two experts, one from measurement and evaluation in the Educational Foundations Department and one from the Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Faculty of Technology Education of the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. Data collected from the study were subjected to Cronbach Alpha reliability index which was used to test and establish the internal consistency of the instrument. The result of the reliability test of all constructs/variables as presented revealed that the Cronbach alpha coefficients of of .823 was obtained. Specifically, the Cronbach alpha coefficient of entrepreneurial status and economic motivation were rated excellent ($>.90$), while business startup was rated ($>.70$). A coefficient of $>.70$ is acceptable (George & Mallery, 2003). Based on the suggestion of Hair *et al.*, (2010), the instrument is reliable for the study.

The questionnaire was administered to the target respondents by the researcher, with the help of three (3) trained research assistants each from the universities. Two hundred and seventy-eight (278) questionnaires were distributed directly to the respondents and two hundred and fifty-two (252) were retrieved representing 90% rate of returned within a period of three weeks. The data collected from the study were analyzed using simple linear regression to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance in order to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variables. The decision rule was based on p-value in the test of the hypotheses, when the p-value was found to be less than the alpha value (0.05) the hypothesis was rejected and when the p-value was found to be greater than the alpha value (0.05) the hypothesis was accepted.

Results and Discussions

Test of hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between entrepreneurial status and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Table 1: Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Status and Business Start-up of Undergraduate Business Education Students of Federal Universities in North-East, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.559 ^a	.313	.312	.435

a. Predictors: (Constant), ES

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	76.704	1	76.704	405.289	.000 ^b
	Residual	168.439	250	.189		
	Total	245.143	251			

a. Dependent Variable: BS

b. Predictors: (Constant), ES

The result on Table 1 reveals $R^2 = 0.313$, $F(1, 250) = 405.289$, $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value is less than the alpha level of the test ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis tested is rejected. The result of null hypotheses in the table indicates that there is significant relationship between entrepreneurial status and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Test of hypothesis two

There is no significant relationship between economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Economic Motivation and Business Start-up of Undergraduate Business Education Students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.499 ^a	.249	.248	.455

a. Predictors: (Constant), EM

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	60.989	1	60.989	294.263	.000 ^b
	Residual	184.047	250	.207		
	Total	245.036	251			

a. Dependent Variable: BS

b. Predictors: (Constant), EM

The result on Table 1 reveals $R^2 = 0.249$, $F(1, 250) = 294.263$, $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value is less than the alpha level of the test ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis tested is rejected. The result from the table indicates that the test of null hypothesis

two revealed that there is significant relationship between economic motivation and business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The result of test of null hypothesis one indicated that entrepreneurial status as independent variable has significant relationship on business start-up as dependent variable of undergraduate business education students of Federal universities in North east, Nigeria. The p-value was found to be less than the alpha value, therefore the hypotheses was rejected. The finding of the study was in line with the submission of Onodugo & Onodugo (2015) who stated that socio-cultural factors are those which have a significant effect on entrepreneurial activities that relate to both society and cultural matters. These include child rearing practices, across cultural difference, cultural deprivation, cultural change, ethnic values, family structure, kingship structure, and regional differences.

The socio-cultural conditions reflect the country's stage of development. Akhter and Sumi (2014); Onodugo and Onodugo (2015) stated that there are some cultures which encourage thrifts and savings among age groups, giving support to in-laws, religious support for the poor, promote hard work and dignity of labour. There are some cultures which at the same time frown at doing business involving alcohol, consumption of pork, drugs, gambling, fishing, saloon business, leather work, and the collection of interest on loan. The various examples mentioned above have an impact on the success of an entrepreneurial business start up.

The result of test of null hypothesis two indicated that economic motivation as independent variable has significant relationship on business start-up as dependent variable of undergraduate business education students of Federal universities in North east, Nigeria. The p-value was found to be less than the alpha value, therefore the hypotheses was rejected. The findings of the research is in tandem with the study of Juliane and Julia (2014) they stated that Entrepreneurs require financial support to diversify their start-up risks, obtain the start-up capital and finance growth and expansion. In many developing and emerging economies there are only few sources for financing and entrepreneurs might be prevented from starting a business as they do not receive the required finances. The need to make money has also been singled out as the main driver leading to individuals pursuing entrepreneurial activities (Kuratko, 2016). Entrepreneurial activities, when pursued strategically, have the capacity to generate high revenue leading to significant profit for the entrepreneur to enjoy, thus Economic motivation comes into the picture.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to examine whether there is relationship between entrepreneurial status, economic motivation and business startup of undergraduate business education students in universities in North east Nigeria. The empirical evidence in this study have shown that there is significant relationship between entrepreneurial status, economic motivation and business startup using entrepreneurial status, economic motivation as the independent variable while Business startup as the dependent variable to the study. The findings of the study will help undergraduate business education students in universities to be prepare and become self-employed, self-reliant rather than job seekers after graduation and this will complement the government efforts and commitments towards entrepreneurship education especially at the tertiary institutions and guarantee the actualization of mission and vision of making entrepreneurship education as mandatory and also achieved the objectives of business education programme in universities in Nigeria. Consequently, the issue of unemployment and

underemployment especially among undergraduate business education students after graduation from the universities can be reduced drastically.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The curriculum planners should ensure planning, maintaining and updating regularly of entrepreneurship content knowledge in the area of entrepreneurship education curriculum to be directed toward inculcating and developing entrepreneurial status for undergraduate business education students in universities so that they become self-employed rather than job seekers after graduation.
2. National University Commission (NUC) should ensure in monitoring and implementation of resources provided for teaching, learning and training of undergraduate business education students entrepreneurship education is geared towards preparing them for business start-up after graduation in order to self-employed.

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